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Software Exports and Market Value Analysis from India

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Abstract

Software export made from India is phenomenal; this paper discussed the revenue, exports, and domestic market of Indian information technology (IT) industry, as well as distribution and export market around the world. The researcher has indented to investigate the mode of software services export to other countries. Adopting the organizational and association evolutionary perspective to examine the market value of IT Industry and software export destination at present, and the potential market in future. Based on Findings the whole scenario of software exports and factual data has been analyzed market size. At last, collectively define the software export market and market value analysis of the Indian software Industry. Implications of the paradigm for software exports and research has examined.

JEL Classification: L80, L86, L89

Keywords: Indian software industry, software exports, IT performance, contribution in GDP

1. Introduction

Over the last three decades, there have been many research paper published related to the software industry in the Indian market. There have been extraordinary elaboration and discussion of the software businesses in India and software export market expansion all over the world(Arora, Arunachalam, Asundi, & Fernandes, 2001). India is competent for stand out in the world to produce the software services at low cost, therefore IT experts are abundant, and needs of resource deployments are more than enough (Pralhad & Hamid, 2007). India is leading in the software services export market, the reason behind an increment of IT export and overall growth rate transparent to understand. Government support, small IT companies setup, IT employees' movement on a large scale and open economy for welcoming all the companies around the world has given such overwhelming results in the software export market. (Athereye 2005), Today, India is one of the top suppliers of IT products and services in the world. Cloud computing and software maintenance services exports from India to all the western countries. Prior to 1984, India's software export policies were guided and guarded by the state-led planned development authorities, however, it got implemented and made some stringent rules to control the fraudulent in IT industry and safe business model(McDowell, 1995). Promotion of software exports and FDI has given importance to expand the Indian IT industry, Special Economic Zone (SEZ) allowed by the government of India to fulfill the basic needs of IT companies.

Comparing with the neighboring countries, India and China has huge potentials in terms of exporting IT services. However, differ in nature of work both countries applied to deal with MNC (Multi-national Companies) clients (Niosi & Tschang, 2008), and both countries are learning to outsource IT projects from advanced nations. Innovative works related to hardware sectors always welcomed in China; however, Information technology-enabled services and software products companies mostly engaged with Indian software companies for IT services to delivery within effective timeline with cheap labor cost. China is good at electronic commodities manufacturing and innovation in the sector of AI (Artificial Intelligence) since the language barrier and labor costing become an obstruction to divert the clients' attention, India favored a huge amount of advantages. India has always preferred by European and American countries for IT businesses and MNCs operations. Dramatically, machine learning has been taken the 2nd position after China in the Asian countries (Bishop, 2006). Since, last 10 years, machine learning has been given new learning scope of data mining, algorithms, and techniques to use for next generation of the world. Compulsiveness has taken a place to learn these ideas and technologies to tackle with competitors in the software export sector. An education system has revamped and re-established under the new pattern of skill learning with new textbook reflected as per the requirements of the IT knowledge.

Among developing countries, India could be a unique example for all the developing nations to learn a fruitful lesson. All the developing nations like the Philippines, Myanmar, Bangladesh, Indonesia and Malaysia having the same trends to supply the labor to rest of the world (Heeks & Nicholson, 2004). India has stated top position among them to supply the best and cheap IT experts to the developed countries for their offshore projects (N. Kumar & Joseph, 2005), government policies and substitutional schemes and government interventions have supported the IT industry. In fact, IT growth has a large amount of contribution to the Indian economy (GDP). Hence, government intervention in the Indian IT industry for subsidies and land acquisitions, special economic zone (SEZ), and smart city development projects are the basic requirements. In the recent years, India has explored the opportunities in the Asian countries including China, which ultimately know for the AI producer and manufacturing hub for the world.

2. Related Literature

There is a large number of literature written by authors on 'software export and market value analyses.' The researcher has driven the key ideas from the IT department of India ("The Information Technology Act, 2008,") and Indian IT literature on software export. Journal has also linked with related thesis published in the area of Indian Software export and Market value analysis. The researcher has deeply studied the NASSCOM database sources and literature (2017th Edition). NASSCOM contributes an overall conceptual idea in the present journal. We have also discussed the Tier-1 published papers (Erumban & Das, 2016) of the IT industry scenario, and it helps to examine the source of Indian economic growth through the IT Industry development. Particularly focusing on the Information & communication technology growth, which is developing new ideas in the software export growth and indirectly contributing in the Indian economy. In the below section, the researcher would like to draw attention to a few literatures and publications for more understanding of the present journal.

In the journal of "Indian Software Industry: Growth patterns, Constraints and Government Initiatives" (Chakraborty & Jayachandran, 2001) researcher studies about the software products and services, export market significance & potential, organizational structure, employment potential, qualitative aspects of software, future opportunity and challenges, market constraints, government policies during 1990s and implementation. This paper has helped to understand the large scale of scenarios of the Indian IT industry, especially in the area of software export and government initiatives towards IT industry. Government policy drives innovation centers in India to increase the software export. It mainly focused on the area of innovation to help IT Industry, especially in the Institute of information technology. We have also captured the database and theoretical knowledge from the 'information technology impact on Indian firms' by (Sabharwal & Sabharwal, 2015) it has discussed India's surge in modern IT service exports. Influences of the exchange rate and microeconomic factors have elaborated economic growth and IT export in the Indian software industry.

In the paper of “Two Scenarios of Indian IT industry” published by (Shyam Sankar & Changat, 2017) in the University of Kerala, India, discussed the employment in Indian IT sector and its importance for economic growth. It also focused on IT shares contribution in the Indian GDP, India's shares in global sourcing market, a different sector of IT industry segment, India's shares in IT services export and overall development of Indian economy with the help of government initiatives. From related theories researcher focused on the government contribution and initiatives done through the various scheme of Information technology and policy amendment department in favor of the IT industry. Overall achievements obtain through the various segment of policies and rebate scheme. There are many more theories have been referenced in this paper to complete the Journal with abundant knowledge of software exports and market value analysis. National Association of software services and computer (NASSCOM, 2016) database references used in the journal as a secondary data model, which helps to elaborate the study in this paper.

3. Software Services Export from India-Recent Trends

Information technology and information technology-enabled services (IT/ITeS) providing companies becoming a largest IT cluster in Indian IT industry. Software export has contributed huge amount of country's positioning to attract the investment from around the world, it has created a number of jobs in India, as well as abroad, like; the USA and European countries (Vijayakumar, 2016), In the last decades Indian IT industry has grown five folds of revenue, meanwhile, it has contributed to country's GDP. In FY2017, IT Industry largely contributed to Indian GDP increased up to > 6.74 percent, and continuously contributing in the FY2018E (7.36%). Indian IT expert is cheaper than other developing countries. Compare to the USA, Indian IT experts are 3-4 times cheaper and effective in terms of process delivery. It has always been Unique Selling Proposition (USP) in the global market (REN21, 2017). Indian IT & ITeS business stands on four pillars: cost-effectiveness, great quality, speedy delivery, and high reliability these are the state art of software industry in India.

In the global market, India growing outsourcing process from western countries, IT-BPM sector booming on a yearly basis. During the FY2017-18, an estimated total value of India's IT & ITeS sector market will increase up to US\$151 billion (excluding Hardware). India's IT-BPM increases up to US\$28.4 billion (of the total IT exports 22% shares). It is a top sourcing destination for FDI, holding 55% of share. India has set up more than 1000 service centers in 200 cities of the 80 countries around the world. Ministry of information technology and electronic department are playing an important role in promoting and supporting the IT organizations with the initiatives of skill development programs and strategic activities. The government support into R&D reflects that investment has taken priority on the research centers and innovation organizations. The government has given full support to the FDI for exploring the opportunities in Indian IT hub (Shenvi, 2011), finance, medical, banking, and electronic products are emerging on the largest scale of BPO and BPM service centers around the world (D. Kumar, 2018). Since India has cheap labor and capable of fulfilling the Client's requirement, thus, engaging on large-scale with international BPOs projects to utilize the resources.

4. Performance of Information Technology & Information Technology Enabled Services

Revenue: Performance of the information technology and information technology-enabled services examined and analyzed through the data retrieve from NASSCOM organization and world economic forum. In the FY2016-17 could see the growth rate \$US141.0 billion increased compare to the last few years (WEF, 2016) average IT growth percentage increased up to 7.0%, it is very obvious demonstration of revenue expenditure in IT & ITeS incredibly increased in 2016-17, as per the estimation (E) of FY2017-18 time period value would be reached up to USD151.0 billion.

Table 1: Revenue growth, IT Department of India-NASSCOM SR-2018, E-Estimate

Year/Description	Export (US\$ billion)	Domestic (US\$ billion)	Total (US\$ billion)
2013-14	87.3	19	106.3
2014-15	97.8	21	118.8
2015-16	107.8	21.7	129.5
2016-17	117	24	141
2017-18	126	25	151
CAGR%(2013-18)	9.60%	7.10%	9.17%

As follows:

$$CAGR = \left(\frac{\text{Ending Value}}{\text{Beginning Value}} \right)^{\left(\frac{1}{\text{\#of years}} \right)} - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Calculation: } & (126 / 87.3)^{1/4} - 1 \\ & = 1.44^{0.25} - 1 \\ & = 1.096 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Export (US\$ billion) CAGR = 0.96 or 9.60%

Above-mentioned data calculated as per the data availability on (meity.gov.in) database, as we can see the results of the export CAGR (compound annual growth rate) US\$ 9.60% which is greater than domestic CAGR US\$ 7.10%, (9.60 > 7.10). By looking at the data (Table 1), we can simply calculate the yearly CAGR, and it seems like export CAGR always higher than domestic CAGR. Total CAGR shows the calculation of export and domestic aggregate growth in the IT industry of India. As this paper elaborates the functioning and emphasis on export statistics, hereby, we can assume that export CAGR always higher than domestic demands and process required in IT and ITeS process. There could be many reasons for small and medium type of Indian IT companies, which are not getting domestic projects from government sectors, like; political loophole for development of infrastructure (smart cities) and not indulging in the digitalization of domestic projects, for more investigation on Indian government policies of IT industry, needs a deep research on Indian IT strategies.

Software export services could be a various mode of services, researcher unable to elaborate all types of services, therefore, it has categories into three parts, IT services, ER&D and software products, and BPO (Business Process Outsourcing). The most recorded IT services export positioned at first place in terms of exporting largest segment of IT services. It holds the 57% of IT export shares, revenue calculated up to US\$ 86 billion; ER&D and software products stands on second position for contributing into the export market 22% of shares in India. BPO sector stands still at third place, sharing up to 21% in Indian IT export market; however, it is emerging faster than IT services, due to its capability of business delivery and coordination with overseas IT partners, it is grooming in all the IT and non-IT centers in India.

Export: IT & ITeS exports increased as per IT department sources(NASSCOM, 2016), in FY 2016-17, US\$ 117.0 billion achieved a great milestone in Indian IT export sector, as per the sources and data analysis, NASSCOM has predicted FY2017-18 estimated growth, that is positively attainable for the IT industry. US\$ 126.0 billion set as a goal of IT export market, which is 7.7% of growth rate compared to last year achieved the target. There are many new projects pouring into IT sector, SMAC (social media, mobility, analytics, and cloud) apart from embedded systems and artificial intelligence, and many new innovative technologies are increasing into IT process.

Figure 1: Export of various segments in IT/ITeS Sector-(Sources NASSCOM SR-2018, E: Estimated)

IT service is the fastest growing segment in the Indian IT industry, Since FY2013-14 it has been increasing faster, accordingly, the number of services and clients have increased in India (Figure1). We can take a couple of statistics FY2015-16 and FY2016-17 IT service export increased from US\$61billion to US\$ 66 billion. As per the consistent growth rate, NASSCOM has estimated IT service export amount up to US\$ 69.3 billion (Figure 2). It is a convincing target for the Industry to achieve. ITeS-BPO and Software products, engineering services and R&D, all these services are burgeoning steadily with a positive remark for exporting IT products and services. As we can see above-mentioned (Figure 2), ITeS-BPO is reinventing itself by exploring the market scope on a yearly basis. Software products and engineering services are also productive and demanding in the export market. In the last five year, R&D centers have increased and reinvented with newly developed technologies to catch up with advanced technologies. R&D expansion has taken as a priority by the Indian government authorities to facilitate the researchers and IT export sector's skills requirement.

Table 2: Industry-Wise Share of ITES/BPO Services Exports (RBI Bulletin, Source-2016)

Activity	Software services exports share in total (%)				
	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
BPO Services	82.0	84.7	82.5	81.9	77.6
Customer interaction services	12.2	14.4	10.9	8.4	4.6
Finance and Accounting, auditing, book keeping, and tax consulting services	13.4	23.5	9.7	11.2	12.2
HR Administration	0.5	0.2	0.9	0.7	0.9
Procurements and logistics	0.5	0.0	0.4	0.3	0.5
Medical transcription	0.6	0.2	0.7	1.4	1.0
Document Management	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.9	0.7
Content development and management and publishing	0.8	0.7	1.4	0.9	0.9
Other BPO service	53.4	45.3	58.0	58.1	56.8
Engineering Services	18.0	15.3	17.5	18.1	22.4
Embedded Solutions	2.4	2.1	4.1	5.3	4.1
Product Design Engineering (mechanical, electronics excluding software)	8.6	7.0	5.9	5.5	5.9
Industrial automation and enterprise asset management	0.6	0.0	2.4	0.2	0.2
Other Engineering service	6.4	6.2	5.1	7.1	12.2
Total	100	100	100	100	100

As per the records of NASSCOM, BPO services expanded in many industries and growing rapidly to facilitate the other service sector by providing them engineering services and BPO services(NASSCOM 2016), In 2016 published Indian IT industry report in NASSCOM association has given a clear picture of the whole IT-BPO Industry. Occupational analysis of IT services written by NASSCOM elaborated on the segment of BPO that is limitless in terms of opportunities in any industry. Like, Finance and accounting, auditing, bookkeeping, and tax consulting services, procurement and logistic, HR administration, medical transcription and document management, etc.... (Table 2) Engineering product services are mainly relevant to the product designing and provide services to the industrial organizations. Engineering services could be in management sector as well for managing industrial assets and enterprise business for the backend process.

Table 3: Organisation-Wise Share of Software (NASSCOM Sources2016)

Organization	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Private Limited Companies	38.5	41.2	35.3	36.0	43.1
Public Limited Companies	61.3	58.7	64.6	63.6	55.6
Others	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.4	1.3
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Organization wise contribution in Indian software services and product exports shows that public companies are having large market shares to contributing in Indian IT export services. Private companies are less active than public limited companies, therefore market shares also differ, and as we can see the yearly growth ratio, public companies seem to have more privileges to attract more IT clients in the Indian market. Since FY2010 until FY2015, public limited companies have done excellent work to facilitate overseas clients and fulfilled their requirements through IT services (Table 3). Public organizations would be stronger in future, however, private sectors will get advantages from IT market boom due to numerous projects pouring into Indian IT hubs(FRPT, 2016). There are a much public-private partnership (PPP) companies and projects initiated for better cooperation with small organizations to lift up its industrious work in IT sector. Knowledge Process Outsourcing(KPO) centers setup all over India dominated with domestic and international projects(NASSCOM, 2014), Jay Ruparel is CEO of Azure knowledge cooperation Pvt, has opened many service centers of KPO process in India and abroad as well. The Azure organization has setup an office in Guangzhou and Xi'an city of China, KPO process deals with all the cross-border projects, regardless of the language obstacles. In India, Azure has setup an office in all the metropolitan cities. There are thousands of employees working in these kinds of KPO process companies.

Since, the 2000s, India has continuously increased the amount of KPO and BPO process, both process having same nature of delivery work to provide the services to clients, however, different from the projects dealing with clients and requirement of IT solutions. KPO does not need much technical knowledge to solve the client's issues; however, it required process knowledge and a basic understanding of technical tools to grab the solution ideas and analytical abilities. BPO deals with two types of business, which categories into voice and non-voice process, non-voice required to have some technical knowledge to solve the technical process. Voice-based BPOs simply dealt with the customer, and resolve issues raised in the system. In these two segments, have lots of process divisions and subdivisions, which could deeply acknowledge through real experience in BPO organizations.

5. Country-Wise Distribution of Software Services Exports

Software services distribution from India is incredibly increasing in the USA, UK and European countries (Figure 3). Approximately 90% of the services exported to these western countries. However, there are new challenges and obstruction burgeoning in these traditional geographic countries. Since 2010, there is a new market emerging from the Asia Pacific, Latin America, and Middle East countries(Srinivasan & Lundqvist, 2010). From the Africa and Asia, opportunities are growing for the Indian IT Industry. Indian IT business expansion is continuously increasing for IT cooperation and collaboration, India has a huge exposure to expand

the IT business in China. Indian ambassador (Gautam Bambawale, 2018) at the launch of Guiyang IT corridor has present a strong case of Indian IT cooperation with China. NASSCOM members and Guiyang authorities have taken needful actions to support the Chinese IT companies to set up the IT business unit in India. China has also reciprocated to setup the IT corridors for cooperation with Indian IT companies.

Figure 2: IT & ITeS exports across geographies (NASSCOM SR-2017-18E)

Indian IT companies have a presence in more than 75 countries in different continents. Most of these are setup in European, American and Asian countries. Generating employment up to 12 billion people around the world. In China more than 10 cities, Indian IT companies are operating IT-BPO projects, which is generating more than 25,000 employment. Both authorities believe that joint hands cooperation needs more work and efforts to establish the large scale of India-China IT corridor. India's second largest IT service provider company (Infosys) has opened first overseas Campus in China and 'Zeta-V' IT Company working on artificial intelligence for language solutions to make a close deal of India and China IT business. 'Zeta-V' practicing innovative language solution for Chinese and Indian professionals to revamp the language barriers for Business requirements. In this way, both countries will join hands together for fulfilling the needs of IT experts and services. NASSCOM an Indian IT business group (China, 27th of May, 2018) has set up Sino-India Digital Collaborative Opportunities Plaza (SIDCOP) in the Tech-hub of Guiyang, southwest of China. IT businesses between both countries started with the milestone of US\$ 6 billion. Final execution of SIDCOP will start in FY2019. Therefore, cooperation with other countries not only benefits Private companies, however, nations are also benefiting to fulfill people's needs and contribute to the economy.

Table 4: Software Business by Foreign Affiliates of Indian Companies (RBI Sources-2016)

Activity	2010-11			2011-12			2012-13			2013-14			2014-15		
	Locally	To India	Other Countries												
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)
IT Services	17.9	0.2	1.6	27.5	10.7	5.4	23.9	1.8	0.4	37.4	2	3	28.5	2.2	3.1
Software Product Development	4.7	0	0.6	1.6	0.7	8	5	2.3	11.2	0	0	14.1	7.4	0.6	16.4
BPO Services	15.2	0.6	9.1	31	4.4	12.3	15.9	0.4	3.6	7.1	0.1	0.2	17.4	2.3	6.2
Engineering Services	1.7	0.3	0	1.5	0.3	20.6	1.6	0.5	0	0.1	0	0	4.5	0	0.1

Other services	338.2	4.4	26.7	391.8	0.4	20.8	307.4	184.6	28.9	644.3	274.6	118.9	783.9	330.6	131.1
Total(₹ billion)	377.7	5.5	38	453.4	16.5	67.1	353.8	189.6	44.1	688.9	276.7	136.2	841.7	335.7	156.9
Total (\$US billion)	8.3	0.1	0.8	9.5	0.3	1.4	6.5	3.5	0.8	11.4	4.6	2.3	13.8	5.5	2.6

6. Software Business of Subsidiaries/Associates

Foreign software companies affiliated under the heads of NASSCOM association, India. It has divided into three parts (locally, to India and other countries), foreign affiliates trade statistics (FATS) has owned total FATS businesses (excluding the services provided in Indian). Following the financial crisis in FY2008, it has moderated. IT business of foreign affiliates Indian companies increased by \$US 5.5 billion compared with \$US 4.6 billion in the previous year (FRPT, 2016). Indian companies provide the IT services in four sectors; IT services, Software product development, BPO services and Engineering services (Table 4), there is another classification 'others services.' Foreign-affiliated companies are the major sources to generate the business outside of India. As per the RBI Sources, foreign-affiliated IT services decrease, however, BPO services, engineering services and software product development emerging on large-scale business.

The USA accounted by the foreign affiliated IT business nearly two-thirds of shares in FY2014-15. Followed by the United Kingdom, Canada, Germany, Singapore, Netherland and other countries of foreign affiliates IT business declined slowly (Table 5, Source; RBI India, 2016).

Table 5: Software Business by Foreign Affiliates of Indian Companies (RBI, Source 2016)

Country	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
USA	67.5	65.0	71.3	65.4	66.7
United Kingdom	6.8	5.3	6.6	7.9	8.0
Canada	2.7	3.6	4.1	4.1	3.3
Germany	2.5	2.9	3.0	3.5	2.4
Singapore	3.4	4.4	2.7	3.3	3.3
Netherlands	3.6	4.3	2.1	3.2	2.3
Other Countries	13.5	14.5	10.2	12.5	14.0
Total (%)	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

In the recent software export statistics (Patil Roopa.s 2016), the traditional software export business model has changed, Middle East countries and Asian regions are burgeoning, countries like; China, Malaysia, Philippines, Indonesia has emerged as a leading IT market.

7. Market Value Analysis

Indian software industry grew up to 7.7% in FY2017, and It contributes 38% in the global outsourcing (IT business), However, future growth estimation (FY2018-E) does not seem to be growing as it should have emerged as a global player. Global businesses are driven by new technologies while traditional business model would be under pressure (Kakkar, 2006). New technology and innovative business model will bring huge disruption in Indian IT industry (Dave, Shelat, Patel, & Jhaveri, 2015). However, Indian IT companies have a decent year (FY2016-17) in terms of financial performance driven by Indian government initiatives like; Make in India and Digital India (digital and non-linear growth model). Indian IT companies more advanced to move up and provide the end-to-end IT service to the clients. The move toward digital technologies will minimize the internal costing in FY2017 and contribute more to generate the revenue (Barn, 2009). However, it will affect the employment sector; companies will not recruit significant numbers of engineers. Digital technologies expected to generate more revenue than traditional techniques of providing IT services to the clients. Indian IT service industry divided into six components (1) software products (2) IT services (3) Engineering and R&D services (4) ITES/BPO (IT-enabled services/Business process outsourcing) (5) Hardware and (6) e-commerce sector. IT services, BPM services, software products, and engineering services are the main IT business for the Indian

market, and the Indian government will benefit significantly from the scheme such a Digital India, Make in India and Start-up India. In the FY2016, the total export value recorded \$US 117 billion, total export value categorized into IT services \$US 66 billion, ITeS-BPO \$US 26 billion and software products, engineering services, R&D \$US 25 billion (NASSCOM-2018).

India's IT industry proposition value unmatched with the world, India's IT-BPO entry level of wages still much lower than in developed countries. India's global delivery centers have increased up to 670 around the world (approximately 78 countries) recorded in FY2017, and the digital-based talents are growing faster. New digital technologies SMAC has changed the way IT business dealt in last decades. Since the government has launched Make in India, Digital India, startup India and many more, IT projects. It is obvious that the government of India is practicing much more in the area of information technology sector to improve the facilities and upgrade the level of delivering services. In the Indian IT Industry, IT experts demands and supply has more gap, many IT experts are losing a job, because of process discontinuity and the expiring contract of clients with Indian IT firms. This is a worry for the all experts in the IT industry(Srinivasan, Lundqvist, & Norström, 2010). However, artificial intelligence and gaming industry is more confident about the future of IT professionals. Artificial intelligence and algorithms, engineering system, data mining, and machine learning have a bright future for IT experts(Sangeetha & Prakash, 2015). In terms of IT export shares, Indian IT services hold shares up to 52% and IT-BPM 38% as per the data recorded in FY2017 (Source RBI, FY2018).

8. Conclusions and Discussion

In the 21st century, the IT industry is an innovative firm for all the businesses input through online portals, particular software/apps. Therefore, Software exports revenue becoming extremely important for the Indian economy (GDP) and generating employment, This paper provides the information of Indian IT exports statistics, as researcher discussed in the section of 'recent trends of Indian IT Industry.' Indian software Industry not only exports the software products and IT services, however, but it also creates many job opportunities within the country and around the world. Aggregate IT exports from India has a huge amount of contribution in Indian economy (GDP), it helps to balance the country's trade deficit and generate the money flow in the domestic economy. Developed countries in America and Europe are utilizing the resource from India by importing IT products and services. In the last few years, traditional IT business model has replaced with new digital technologies, it is more effective for producing IT products and services. Moreover, minimize the cost of IT products and service delivery time. Statistics are the evidence of the growth rate of software export from India FY2016-17, total export revenue generated up to \$US 117 billion as per the NASSCOM statistics. At present, FY2017-18E software exports revenue expected to increase by \$US 126 billion. Total market value of IT industry in FY2017-18 Estimated up to \$US 151 billion (NASSCOM-2018). Discussion of this paper contains a lot of new sources to prove the importance of software exports. In the section on the performance of Indian IT industry total revenue divided into two parts, export, and domestic market. The total expenditure of the IT revenue has calculated with the CAGR to figure out the individual percent of the export amount and domestic market of India. Entertainment and media industry emerged steadily in past few years(Entertainment Software Association 2015) it has reflected the habits of new generations for using media and entertainment products, SMAC developing new products based on the trends growing in media and entertainment industry.

The researcher has divided software service provider's background (Private Limited and Public limited) to know more about the IT service providers financial and production capability for delivering services to overseas clients. Following that researcher has captured the data for elaborating Country-Wise software service exports. We analysis the traditional geographical countries of software export business are taking a move to other countries, such as Africa and Asia continent. New market in China and Japan are continuously exploring the IT business cooperation (China SIPCOP establishment, 2018). It is a symbol of India-China IT collaboration and future cooperation of IT services. In view of overseas companies' settlement in India, the researcher has discussed the foreign affiliated IT companies in India, which all are growing rapidly and utilizing the cheapest resources, and facilities given under the IT policy amendments, the government of India. Therefore, it is obvious that why foreign affiliated companies are establishing in India. In the section of market value analysis, we have

deeply researched about the overall IT market value and its export statistics. In the FY2016, the total export value recorded \$US 117 billion, total export value categories into IT services \$US 66 billion, ITeS-BPO \$US 26 billion and software products, engineering services, R&D \$US 25 billion (NASSCOM-2018). Indian IT market value has huge scope for mutual benefits and IT business cooperation in the next decade. Overall, the study of the software export and market value analysis discovered another area of study in Indian IT Industry. There is a need to research on Indian government policies behind the growth rate of software exports and the FDI schemes to expand more MNCs in Indian IT industry. Finally, Investment revenue from the government sector and FDI will help to expand the Indian IT industry and indirectly increase the software export revenue; moreover, the government itself takes advantage in the various sector of Indian economy.

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